

AUTOMATIC POSITIONING OF A MOBILE SOLAR POWER PLANT UNDER LONG-TERM SHADING

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ABSTRACT *The purpose of this study is to develop efficient automatic control systems for mobile solar power plants with minimal energy consumption of computing facilities in conditions of prolonged shading. A block diagram of an efficient solar mobile power plant has been developed that provides electrical energy to household appliances, low-power engines, a digital automatic control system for the angular displacement of solar panel batteries, which operates autonomously in conditions of long-term shading with extrapolation of the angular trajectory of the sun. The accuracy of control and transient processes of a combined tracking system with different orders of astatism is estimated. The most acceptable system was chosen for the entire time interval of daylight hours.*

Ключевые слова: длительное затенение, структурная схема, пеленгационная характеристика, экстраполятор, замкнутый контур

АННОТАЦИЯ *Целью данного исследования является разработка эффективных автоматических систем управления мобильных солнечных энергетических установок с минимальным потреблением энергии вычислительных средств в условиях длительного затенения. Разработана структурная схема эффективной солнечной мобильной энергетической установки, обеспечивающей электрической энергией бытовые приборы, двигатели малой мощности, цифровой автоматической системы управления угловым перемещением батарей солнечных панелей, автономно работающей в условиях длительного затенения с экстраполяцией угловой траектории*

солнца. Произведена оценка точности управления и переходных процессов комбинированной следящей системы с разными порядками астатизма. Была выбрана наиболее приемлемая система на всем интервале времени светового дня.

***Keywords:** long-term shading, block diagram, direction-finding characteristic, extrapolator, closed loop*

INTRODUCTION

The depletion of fossil energy resources and the growing difficulties in solving environmental problems of energy development lead to the need to search for new, non-traditional methods of obtaining energy. Among them, the most promising is the photoelectric method of converting solar energy. A mobile power plant is especially necessary for information and household appliances in places remote from large populated villages, in mountainous areas.

Mobile solar power plants can also serve to power low-power motors. The spread of angles when deploying the installation on the ground, binding to the orientation angles relative to the initial position of the sun should not exceed $\pm 15^\circ$. The installation should work in automatic mode. [1-5].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The first stage of work on the creation of a device for automatic positioning of a solar panel and tracking the direction of the maximum light flux (hereinafter referred to as the tracker) was the analysis and generalization of the existing experience in improving the efficiency of solar installation operation [6–9]. The main sources of information were scientific articles, collections of conferences on renewable energy sources and interactive resources. The task of the analysis was to theoretically substantiate the possibility of increasing the efficiency of the solar panel by changing their positioning during operation.

Based on the results of the analysis, a generalization was carried out, which made it possible to exclude specific and particular solutions in the field of increasing

the efficiency of the solar panel, as well as to identify a general trend in ways to increase their efficiency and performance [10-12].

RESULTS

The principle of determining the angular coordinates and the sensor of angular mismatches for automatic tracking of the sun in conditions of long-term shading and other interferences have been developed. The operation of a solar power plant depends on the position of the sun relative to the surface of the panels with photovoltaic plates. The highest efficiency of solar cells is achieved when the sun's rays fall on the surface of the plates vertically, so a system of automatic tracking and angular movement of photocell panels is needed. In the case of prolonged occultation of the sun by clouds, extrapolation of the angles of the sun's position is applied. The angle of deviation from the true position of the sun should not go beyond the antenna pattern. Moreover, in order to save energy, it is beneficial to have high accuracy in order to ensure smooth movement of the photocell platform, eliminating unwanted transients [13].

The automatic control system contains an antenna system - an angular mismatch sensor, an extrapolator and an electric frame rotation drive with photovoltaic panels and a fixed antenna.

The input signal to the control system is the angular position of the sun. The system has two independent control channels for azimuth and elevation, respectively. The flat surface of photosensitive panels with a rigidly fixed lobe antenna rotates within 180° during daylight hours with the help of an automatic tracking system (1).

A function that simulates the angular displacement of the sun has the form:

$$\varepsilon(t) = [90 - 90 \cos(0.1 * t)] * [1(t) - 1(t - 10)] \quad (1)$$

The most favorable operating mode of the installation is continuous tracking in a closed loop. In case of sun shading, the combined tracking mode is used. During shading, the closed tracking mode is interrupted and the open tracking mode is switched on by extrapolating the angular position of the sun for the shading time according to the coordinates and its derivatives stored by the extrapolation filter. When shading ends, closed loop tracking mode is enabled. The block diagram of the control loop is shown in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Structural diagram of automatic tracking solar power plant

In this figure, the input signal is the position of the sun in elevation (in azimuth), the noise is the shading of the sun by clouds. As a result, closed-loop auto-tracking is interrupted. This is simulated in the diagram using an interrupt block.

The tracking error signal sensor in the corners is one of the main elements of the system for automatically orienting the photovoltaic panels of the power plant in the direction of the sun. In general, the problem of determining angles is spatial. We will restrict ourselves to two coordinates: in elevation and in azimuth. The most important element of an automatic system for tracking the position of the sun is an antenna - a sensor of angular coordinates in azimuth and elevation, respectively.

In the general case, when the antenna is not directed to the sun, but has a large deviation φ from the axis of the parabola (from the optical axis of the antenna), the current induced by sunlight in the photocell will be equal to:

$$I = K * S * \sin(\alpha + \varphi) \quad (2)$$

where S is the area of the photosensitive element, K is the sensitivity of the element (the dimension is mA, per unit area of the photocell). To calculate the effective area, it is necessary to know the angles of incidence of the rays α on the parabolic surface, depending on the distance of the element from the central point of the parabola. The angles of incidence of the rays α on the surface of the parabola are:

$$\alpha = \arccos \frac{R}{\sqrt{R^2 + (2p)^2}} \quad (3)$$

DISCUSSION

The difference in the values of the signals of the photocells of the opposite petals of the antenna, normalized by the sum of these signals, form the direction, finding characteristic of the petal antenna. It is shown in fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Direction finding characteristic of the angle sensor

The angular sensor is made by spraying an amorphous light-sensitive material on a base that repeats the profile of a parabola and is structurally attached to the frame of the photocell panels. Its dimensions are chosen so as to provide a sufficient amount of photosynthesis current for satisfactory operation of the input electronic amplifier and analog-to-digital converter.

The extrapolator is used to generate accurate closed-loop tracking and to extrapolate the signal during interruption. The extrapolator plays an important role, especially during the period of sun eclipse when the error signal is zero, i.e. the loop is actually open, and tracking should continue on the signals of this device.

The extrapolator affects not only the tracking accuracy in closed and open modes, but also transients, so when the system is analyzed as a whole, all elements of the tracking system are taken into account.

The input signal of the system - the angular position of the sun and the maximum tracking error during daylight hours with continuous shading for 2.4 hours is shown in Fig. 3(a) and fig. 3(b), respectively.

Fig. 3 (a). Input signal
(angular position of the sun)

Fig. 3 (b). Tracking error
with continued shading for 2.5 hours

The value of the tracking error without shading of the sun does not exceed 0.13 degrees over the entire interval of daylight hours. The worst working conditions - when shading in the time interval from 9 hours to 12 hours. The largest error reaches nine degrees (see Fig. 3(b)). As a result of the analysis, it was concluded that the system works satisfactorily throughout the entire daylight hours with sun shading up to two hours and forty minutes.

CONCLUSION

In the course of this work, a combined control system for automatic tracking of the sun in conditions of prolonged shading was developed. Directional diagrams of angular sensors with a linear direction-finding characteristic in a given range of angles were formed. The value of the error of automatic tracking without shading of the sun is calculated for the entire interval of daylight hours. Creation of the principle of precise automatic control based on extrapolation with a theoretically infinitely high order of astatism.

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